

Policy Brief – March 2026

ANALYSING FARMERS' MOTIVATIONS REGARDING DIGITALISATION

Highlights

- Farm digitalisation can improve efficiency, sustainability and the attractiveness of farming, but adoption remains uneven.
- Farmers value time savings, better decision-making and new business models, yet face high costs, skills gaps and trust problems.
- Small and medium-sized farms are most vulnerable to being excluded from digital benefits.
- Policies must move beyond technology promotion and focus on skills, infrastructure, affordability and data governance.
- A farmer-centred digital transition can support both competitiveness and environmental goals.

Context of the issue

European agriculture is increasingly expected to meet productivity, environmental and climate objectives. Digital technologies such as sensors, farm management software, robotics and data-based decision tools are promoted as key solutions (Klerkx et al., 2019).

According to Iliopoulos et al. (2025), farm digitalisation is not solely a technological process but constitutes a broader transformation of farm management practices, professional identities and governance relationships. Although

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stakeholders widely acknowledge the potential benefits of digital tools, significant barriers continue to limit their effective and equitable adoption.

These barriers include high investment and operating costs, limited access to digital skills and training, insufficient rural connectivity, persistent distrust towards technology providers and public institutions, and uncertainty regarding data ownership and control (Iliopoulos et al., 2025; Rotz et al., 2019). These challenges are particularly pronounced for small and medium-sized farms and in regions with limited digital infrastructure (Iliopoulos et al., 2025; Klerkx et al., 2019).

This policy brief addresses the question:

How can European policy ensure that farm digitalisation is economically viable, socially acceptable and environmentally effective?

Key challenges identified include:

- High investment and maintenance costs.
- Lack of digital skills and training opportunities.
- Poor rural connectivity.
- Low trust in technology providers and institutions.
- Uncertainty over ownership and use of farm data.

If these challenges are not addressed, digitalisation risks reinforcing existing inequalities between large and small farms and between regions.

Policy Recommendations

Strengthen skills and advisory services

Our findings indicate that farmers perceive digitalisation as requiring new competences related to data interpretation, technology management and strategic decision-making. Participants reported limited availability of accessible and tailored training programmes, particularly for older farmers and small-scale producers. Policy measures should therefore:

- Develop continuous, practice-oriented digital training programmes for farmers.
- Expand digital farm advisory services that integrate technical, agronomic and business support.
- Prioritise support for small farms and older farmers, where digital literacy gaps are greatest.

Improve rural digital infrastructure

Inadequate broadband and mobile network coverage was consistently identified as a structural barrier to digital adoption. Farmers reported that unreliable connectivity constrains the use of real-time data applications, cloud-based platforms and digital monitoring systems, even when such technologies are available. Policy should therefore:

- Accelerate investment in broadband and mobile networks in rural areas.
- Align infrastructure funding with agricultural digital strategies to ensure practical usability.

Reduce financial barriers

High initial investment requirements, ongoing maintenance costs and the risk of rapid technological obsolescence were among the most frequently cited constraints. These challenges disproportionately affect small and medium-sized farms, for which investment risks are more difficult to absorb. Policy instruments should:

- Provide targeted subsidies or low-interest loans for farm-level digital tools.
- Promote modular and upgradeable technologies to reduce risks linked to rapid obsolescence.

Ensure transparent data governance

Concerns related to data ownership, access and control constitute a central source of distrust towards digitalisation. Farmers expressed apprehension that technology providers and large commercial actors may appropriate farm-generated data without corresponding benefits for primary producers. Policymakers should:

- Establish clear rules guaranteeing farmer control over farm-generated data.
- Require technology providers to ensure transparent pricing, interoperability and long-term support.

Promote inclusive digital ecosystems

Digitalisation can enhance cooperation, improve the social image of farming and attract younger generations, provided that it is embedded within supportive institutional environments. Policy should therefore:

- Support cooperative and shared digital platforms to lower costs and encourage peer learning.
- Expand participatory innovation approaches (e.g. Living Labs) where farmers co-design technologies.

Evidence and Analysis

The findings are based on 18 focus groups held in Living Labs across Europe (Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Poland, Spain, UK), involving farmers, advisors, policymakers, researchers and technology providers.

Perceived Benefits

Participants associate digitalisation with:

- Time savings and efficiency through automation and real-time data.
- Improved planning and decision-making.
- New business models, including traceability and direct sales.
- Better image of farming, attracting young people and women.
- Environmental benefits, such as reduced input use and waste.

Perceived Costs and Risks

Main concerns include:

- High investment and operating costs, especially for small farms.
- Learning effort and additional workload related to data management.
- Rapid technological obsolescence.
- Low trust towards governments, consultants and technology providers.
- Unclear data ownership and governance, creating fear of dependence on large firms.

Key Insight

Farmers' willingness to adopt digital tools depends not only on performance but also on institutional support, trust and fairness. Where training, infrastructure and governance are weak, digitalisation is seen as risky and burdensome rather than beneficial.

Limitations

The evidence reflects stakeholder perceptions from qualitative research and does not measure economic impacts directly. However, the multi-country design ensures strong relevance for European policymaking.

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